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D6.2 Ethical application documents for JRA2

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The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
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3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
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7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT INDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands
18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
JRA	Joint Research Activity
AHA	Active and Healthy Ageing
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. VITALISE brings together Living Labs across Europe (and 1 outside Europe in Canada) to create a Thematic ecosystem of Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain, aiming at creating synergies and transnational collaboration opportunities through innovative Joint Research Activities.

During VITALISE three Joint Research Activities will be implemented among the consortium Living Lab partners. These Joint Research Activities (JRAs) include state of the art use cases that investigate Active and Healthy Ageing (AHA) and chronic conditions in three important domains for the Health and Wellbeing Research. They were selected based on the consortium’s existing research studies and expertise: Rehabilitation, Transitional care and Everyday living environments (WP5, WP6, WP7). This document presents the work performed for obtaining ethical approval for the research activities performed in WP6, JRA2 Transitional care.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of JRA2

The Joint Research Activities (JRAs) will serve as the test bed for all the internal harmonization procedures, for assessing and improving the provided services, as well as the research cases that could be the basis for the external researchers through the trans-national and virtual access procedures. JRA2 (performed in WP6) will be studying the feasibility and benefit of collecting multichannel data across Living Labs on the topic of transitional care and to harmonize data processes and collection. It is a multicenter, prospective, observational cohort study that will consist of three phases, running consecutively in multiple sites: a cocreation phase, a testing and simulation phase, and a transnational pilot phase. The cocreation phase aims to build a common understanding among different sites, investigate the differences in hospitalization discharge management among countries, and the willingness of different stakeholders to use technological solutions in the transitional care process. The testing and simulation phase aims to explore ways of integrating observation of a patient's clinical condition, patient involvement, and discharge education in transitional care. The objective of the simulation phase is to evaluate the feasibility and the barriers faced by health care professionals in assessing transition readiness. The simulation phase pilot will be performed in Finland while the small scale pilot study will run across 3 countries (Greece, Canada, Spain)

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document describes all the documents prepared for ethics approval application in the different sites of the multicenter pilot. It also includes information about the incidental findings policy that is applied in the project. As the incidental findings and ethical applications procedures are common within the three JRAs of VITALISE, this deliverable presents some duplication with D5.2 and D7.2. However, we believe that a coherent document for each JRA is important.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the JRA2 transnational study protocol and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** describes the incidental findings policy of VITALISE JRAs
- **Section 3** describes the ethical submission of each of the different partners in this JRA.
- **Section 4** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable

2 Incidental findings policy

The consent forms which have been submitted for ethics approval include the following incidental findings policy, as described in 5.1.6 of VITALISE Grant Agreement No.101007990:

Main ethical challenge arises when trying to identify when it is ethically permissible or obligatory to disclose or not disclose incidental findings to patients or research participants and how to manage such process.

Four ethical principles are found to be relative to this issue:

1. Principle of respect for persons: which recognizes the fundamental human capacity for rational self-determination;
2. Principle of beneficence: that “calls on professionals to take actions to ensure the wellbeing of others”;
3. Principle of justice and fairness: that requires fair and equitable treatment of all;
4. Principle of intellectual freedom and responsibility: that “...protects sustained and dedicated creative intellectual exploration that furthers scientific progress, while requiring that practitioners take responsibility for their actions.”

In general, an Incidental Finding (IF) is considered to be “a finding concerning an individual research participant that has potential health or reproductive importance and is discovered in the course of conducting research but is beyond the aims of the study. This means that IFs may be on variables not directly under study and may not be anticipated in the research protocol.”

The VITALISE project will adopt and implement the following IFs procedure:

1. The potential participant will be made aware that incidental findings are possible during the process of informed consent. Also, the potential participant will be made aware whether such findings will be disclosed, the process for disclosing these findings, and whether and how participants might opt out of receiving certain types of findings. The potential participant will be given the option to nominate a doctor of their choosing to whom the IFs should be disclosed.
2. If a potential incidental finding is spotted, the researchers will verify such finding. Following verification, the researchers will consult an expert to determine whether a. there is an IF, b. it is significant for the participants health to mandate disclosure
3. If disclosure is mandated, the researchers will take into account the participant’s wishes as expressed in their consent form.

This incidental findings policy adheres to all ethical principles identified as relevant. The policy applies also in cases where the participants lack the capacity for consent, where the legal representative will opt in or out for disclosure of potential incidental findings. The policy will not be implemented in the event that local legislation mandates IFs disclosure regardless of the participant’s wishes (ex. threat of life).

3 Ethical submission processes and files

This section presents the processes that have been followed for the ethical submission in each different country and institutions. As the processes vary even within different institutions in the same country each partner was asked to provide the following information:

- Which documents are required for the ethical submission in your case, what are the compulsory and optional documents?
- What is included in each document? Please add a small, generic description for the scope, aim and information included in each document. No need for detailed structure description on a variable level. Does the document have a specific compulsory structure or can it follow “free structure”?

- Which is the ethical committee that you submit your ethical application? Please provide a name and structural information (e.g., established internally in your organization, the university committee)
- Website for the ethical committee (if any exists)
- What is the process of submission, dates that the committee is meeting/deciding?
- Do you receive any consultation before the submission? If yes, by whom and what did it include.
- When is the first decision expected?

Furthermore, specific considerations were given to all partners in order to ensure the successful completion of the VITALISE project. More specifically:

- Based on the VITALISE GA, external researchers that will join the Living Lab infrastructures may propose specific analysis to already existing data gathered during the JRAs.
- Synthetic data generated from the data gathered in the JRAs should become available in the RAI system and data discovery portal. Moreover, raw data gathered in the JRAs should become available for analysis in the RAI system and data discovery portal.
- Data for Virtual Access (WP12). “VITALISE will develop access policies based on permissions or licenses granted by data owners, allowing a range of options for contribution and data sharing”. In that sense, please consider if your data could be fully anonymized without losing required information for your analysis. The pseudo-anonymized data should become available for processing through the VITALISE data discovery portal.

3.1 Informed consent procedures

The informed consent procedures to be followed by all partners during the execution of the JRA2 studies is described in chapter 4 of Deliverable 14.1 as submitted to the commission in M8 of the project.

3.2 Simulation phase in LAUREA simulated hospital (Finland)

Simulation-based research planned to be conducted in Laurea does not involve patients or healthcare service users. The participants are nursing students in Laurea University of Applied Science, thus it is not considered as medical research. According to Finnish National Board on Research Integrity¹, and The Human Sciences Ethics Committee of the Helsinki Region Universities of Applied Sciences² the ethical review statement for non-medical research with human participants is required in the following circumstances:

1. Participation in the research deviates from the principle of informed consent
2. The research involves intervention in the physical integrity of the research participants
3. The research involves minors under the age of 15 who participate without the separate consent of their guardian or without the guardian being informed, based on which the guardian would have the opportunity to forbid the child from participating,
4. The research participants will be subjected to exceptionally strong stimuli
5. The research involves the risk of causing mental harm that exceeds the limits of normal daily life to the research participants or their family members or others closest to them
6. The research could pose a threat to the safety of the research participants or the researchers, or their family members or others closest to them.

The planned simulation-based research does not contain any of the aforementioned features, and therefore, there is no need for requesting ethical review statement. However, research permit from

¹ https://tenk.fi/sites/default/files/2021-01/Ethical_review_in_human_sciences_2020.pdf

² <https://www.metropolia.fi/en/rdi/ethics-committee>

Laurea University of Applied Sciences is required³. The documents attached in the application include :

- Research plan
 - Description of participants recruitment, simulation intervention, data collection and analysis procedures and ethical considerations
- Interview outline, student feedback questionnaire and outline of observation sheet (included in the research plan)
- Information document for the participants (in Finnish)
- Consent form for the participants (in Finnish)
- Privacy statement (in Finnish)

No consultation before the submission was received because the instructions concerning the need of ethical review and research permit are clear and informative. The application has been sent 31.1.2022. The application will be processed usually within two weeks (no fixed meeting/decision dates), and the research permit was granted on 31 January 2022. The proof of approval can be found in ANNEX 1.

3.3 Small scale pilot in AUTH Healthcare transitions Living Lab (Greece)

Part of the transnational small-scale pilot study for transition in care will be conducted by AUTH in Greece. The study was submitted to the *Committee on Research Ethics and Conduct* of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EHDE AUTH), or Ethics Committee RC AUTH as it is usually called (<https://www.rc.auth.gr/ed/>). This was established in accordance with law N. 4521/2018 of the Greek government (articles 21-27 Chapter 5 – Committees on Research Ethics and Conduct) in 2018. It falls under the umbrella of the Research Committee of AUTH and is comprised by five (5) permanent members of staff of AUTH and two (2) external associates.

When submitting an application to the ethical committee of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki the following documents should be filled in:

- Application form signed by the scientific coordinator. The application form follows a specific structure (it can be found and downloaded [here](#)). Only the scientific coordinator's information and contact details, as well as the name of the research project and funding agency should be filled in.
- Research protocol. The research protocol does not have a compulsory structure but it should at least provide the following information:
 - a. Introduction, study objectives and rationale
 - b. Inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as where and how recruitment will take place
 - c. Brief outline of the personal information and data that will be collected
 - d. A Summary of the methods, equipment and technologies that will be used to collect the personal information and data. (If PROMs/PREMs are to be used their names and domain should be provided. If interviews are to be carried out a mock-up of the interview's structure should be outlined).
 - e. How participants' confidentiality will be maintained throughout and after the completion of the study.
- The declaration of legal and ethical compliance that has a standard structure (it can be found and downloaded [here](#)). Only the scientific coordinator's information and contact details, as well as the name of the research project and funding agency should be filled in.
- Ethics self-assessment Questionnaire. The Ethics self-assessment questionnaire has a compulsory structure (it can be found and downloaded [here](#)). This document requires the applicant to provide a summary of the research protocol and reply to yes or no questions

³ <https://www.laurea.fi/en/research/research-permits/>

concerning several topics e.g. funding, participants (human or animal), personal data that will be collected etc.. In some cases the applicant must provide additional information in open fields, as directed by the document, e.g., in the case of personal data if data are to be imported and/or exported from and/or to non-EU countries further details about the countries and the data to be imported/exported should be provided

- Participant's informed consent form (if required) accompanied by the information form and other information material that will be given to the participants before obtaining their consent. The participant's informed consent also has a compulsory structure (it can be found and downloaded [here](#)). There are empty fields where the participant (or the participant's legal guardian) may add their information. The applicant should have pre-filled in the name of the research project/study, the project's ID as registered in the Special Account for Research Funds of AUTH and specify that the participants will be briefed on the use of devices/medicines/equipment/etc., that the participants will need to use during their involvement in the research project.

The information form does not need to follow a specific format, but it must contain the following:

- a. Name of research project/study
- b. Name and contact details of scientific coordinator
- c. Funding agency
- d. DPO contact details
- e. Basic information about the project/study
- f. Assurances that their care from their doctor will not be affected by their decisions
- g. The rationale and objectives of the study
- h. Why they have been invited to participate
- i. What their participation may cost them
- j. A detailed explanation of research procedures concerning their participation
- k. What data will be collected and for how long they will be maintained.
- l. Who will have access to their data
- m. A clear description of any possible risks (will the participant face any danger, will the participant experience any pain)
- n. An overview of the possible benefits participants may gain from their involvement in the study
- o. A summary of the incidental findings handling policy
- p. A brief overview of the project/study dissemination plans
- q. A detailed description of their rights (i.e., participation is voluntary, consent can be retracted at any time, personal data may be deleted upon request etc.)

Any other information material is freely structured and depend on the needs of the project/study.

- Required approval(s) from other competent authorities (e.g. of another institution) (if required). The structure of the approval(s) from other competent authorities depends on the authority issuing the approval (signed document, certificate, declaration etc.).

There is no specific schedule that applicants need to abide by to submit the applications. They (the scientific coordinator/project manager or someone on their behalf and with their explicit agreement) need to submit the abovementioned documents electronically to the address ethics@rc.auth.gr. Pursuant to article 23 par. 4 of law 4521/2018 the Ethics Committee RC AUTH should discuss the requests and reach a decision (i.e., approve, or make recommendations and suggestions for revisions, if moral and ethical obstacles arise), or request additional information within a reasonable time that cannot exceed fifteen (15) days from the submission of the application and all accompanying documents. If the 15 day period passes and the committee hasn't replied, the application is considered approved. Two avenues are available for consultation in an unofficial format. Regarding matters about data protection consultation is provided by the DPO of AUTH, for

all other matters the committee accepts requests for consultation and responds usually within a week.

The ethical submission for the protocol was done in 11/03/2022 and proof is included in ANNEX 1. The acceptance of the ethical submission was also received in 28/03/2022.

3.4 Small scale pilot in McGill–Université de Montréal Biomedical Research and Informatics Living Laboratory for Innovative Advances of New Technologies (Canada)

The study requested approval from the CRIR Research Ethics Board (REB)⁴. The REB is designated by Quebec's Minister of Health and Social Services under Article 21 of the Civil Code of Quebec, allowing the REB to evaluate projects involving a minor or a person of full age who is incapable of giving consent. It is constructed in accordance with the "Regulations concerning the Creation and Operation of the Research Ethics Board for the CRIR Institutions" (Règlement portant sur la création et le fonctionnement du CÉR des établissements du CRIR). The "REB Internal Management Rules and Regulations" (Règles de régie interne) define the REB functioning modalities. The REB is recognized by the three universities affiliated with CRIR: McGill University, Université de Montréal and Université du Québec à Montréal).

The documents that are submitted to the ethical committee are:

- Research protocol: the structure is free but there are sections that must be included (i.e. Introduction, Objectives, Methods (participant description and recruitment), Procedure, Data collection and analysis, Dissemination of results, Feasibility, Budget, Timeline)
- Consent form(s): there is a template that we are strongly recommended to follow (a copy can be downloaded [here](#))
- A copy of (or link to) all PROMs and PREMs used in the study
- There are various forms that must be completed on the Nagano platform
- Scientific evaluation (either from a funding agency or by the local scientific evaluation committee, if the study has not been funded)
- Recruitment procedure form⁵ (optional)

All new projects and management of current projects (requests for modifications, renewals, project closures) is done directly in the Nagano platform. All forms are completed on the platform and all required documents are uploaded there as well. The committee meets approximately once per month to evaluate applications submitted.

The ethical submission for the protocol was done beginning of March and the ethical committee requested some additional information. The proof from the last communication (18/3/2022) is included in ANNEX 1.

3.5 Small scale pilot in LifeSTech Living Lab (Spain)

The study requested approval by the Comité de Ética de actividades de I+D+i de la UPM⁶. The purpose of the Ethics Committee for R&D&I that operates at the UPM is to evaluate the ethical consequences or problems of research, development or technological innovation work carried out at the UPM and whose funding (competitive projects) is to be obtained in public calls for which the authorisation of the UPM itself is required, or in calls organised by the University's own R&D programme. The documents that are submitted to the committee are:

⁴ <https://crir.ca/en/ethics/the-research-ethics-board-reb-in-brief/>

⁵ <https://crir.ca/en/ethics/documentation/>

⁶ <https://www.upm.es/internacional/Researchers/ResearchSupport/EthicsCommittee>

- **Identification of ethical issues in projects, contracts, grants or partnerships** (specific compulsory structure). It is the first mandatory document that must always be filled in (mod 6). It involves ticking YES/NO in response to several questions related to the following areas: protection of personal data, research involving human subjects, research involving animals, research involving biological agents, research involving chemical agents, research involving genetically modified organisms, research involving radioactive substances, environmental risks, research involving human embryos or fetuses. If the answer is YES to any of the questions referring to any of these areas, new specific documents must be submitted.
- **Request for a report on ethical issues affecting research involving human subjects** (specific compulsory structure). Request for a report on ethical aspects affecting research involving human subjects: description of the project, what is being researched, objective and methodology of the study. Specifically, this document details if there is the involvement and use of samples of human origin or involving the use of cells and tissues of the human embryonic origin or cell lines derived from them.
- **Request for a report on ethical issues related to research involving human subjects: protection of personal data and privacy** (specific compulsory structure). This document describes and details several aspects of the collection and protection of participants' personal data, as well as the management and custody of the data collected during the study.

To initiate the process of evaluating an activity that requires an Ethics Committee report, the principal investigator should follow the steps below:

- Create a first pdf file including the assessment application forms: Form 6 and the specific documents for their area (these can be downloaded at the bottom of this page).
- Create a second pdf file with the remaining documentation for the projects needed for their evaluation.
- Send the two pdf files to secretaria.adjunto.vinvestigacion@upm.es.
- Submit a copy of the two files via UPM's General Registry.

The Committee has the authority to request from the main researcher of a project under assessment any additional information, in as many iterations, as it deems necessary to execute its duties. Ordinary Committee meetings will be held twice a year. However, the first response is expected within 2-3 months.

The ethical submission for the protocol was done on 7/2/2022 and proof is included in ANNEX 1. Until then the team went through some rounds of clarifications regarding

- Data. Some clarifications regarding data collection, access control and storage.
- End-users. More details on the user recruitment strategy and provide the consent form for recruiting.

The final approval is expected within next weeks.

3.6 Small scale pilot in CERTH–Information Technologies Institute Near-Zero Energy Building Smart Home (Greece)

The study was submitted for approval by the Ethical Committee of CERTH which is internally established by the Board decision. It consists of five (5) members. At least two of these members, must not be affiliated with CERTH and at least one member must be specialized in Ethics or Bioethics. The knowledge background of the committee members should, as far as possible, reflects the disciplines and scopes of CERTH. The term of their duties lasts three (3) years and is renewable only once. The compulsory documents concern:

- the approval of the study conduct
- the consent and information procedures with respect to the voluntary participation of humans in the study

- ethics protocol which initiates clear ethical guidelines and principles.

The compulsory documents (consent form and information sheet) necessarily include a questionnaire and a brief report regarding the adequacy and compliance of the research project with the applicable legislation. In this report, the scientific supervisor determines whether the purpose and methodology of the research project are in the light of the Principles of Ethics and legislation. Ethical considerations are a main part of the experimental procedure of nZEB LL. In this respect our study will be carried out in accordance with the ethical conduct and juridical national and EU laws.

The issues to be approved by the Ethical Committee are sent electronically to the secretary of the Committee appointed by the Board decision. The secretary is in charge to notify the committee members regarding the agenda. The committee meets regularly once (1) a month and extraordinarily whenever requested by its Chairman, the Chairman of the Board of the research body. The committee may meet remotely by electronic means, as necessary.

The ethical submission for the protocol was done 31/3/2022 and proof is included in ANNEX 1.

4 Conclusion

This document provided an overview of procedures and submissions in relation to ethics approval application in multicenter pilot study in WP6. The descriptions that were collected will also serve as input in WP2 in order to understand the commonalities and differences of each ethical procedure and investigate the creation of common templates that can facilitate the process in Living Labs.

It is important to point out that the ethical submissions were done on time and no delay is expected in the pilot phase implementation of WP6. All the partners participating in JRA2 are included in this deliverable.

Annex 1

Proof of ethics submission by AUTH

Διευκρίνιση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου

Οι πληροφορίες που συμπεριλαμβάνονται σε αυτό το μήνυμα είναι εμπιστευτικές και η χρήση τους επιτρέπεται μόνον από τον αναφερόμενο παραλήπτη. Εάν έχετε λάβει το παρόν μήνυμα από λάθος και δεν είστε ο προοριζόμενος παραλήπτης, σας ενημερώνουμε ότι αποκάλυψη, αναπαραγωγή, διανομή ή οποιασδήποτε άλλης μορφής χρήση των περιεχομένων του παρόντος μηνύματος απαγορεύεται. Επίσης παρακαλείσθε να αποστείλετε το αρχικό μήνυμα στην διεύθυνση του αποστολέα, καθώς και στη συνέχεια να διαγράψετε το μήνυμα από το σύστημά σας.

Η επικοινωνία μέσω Διαδικτύου δεν είναι ασφαλής και επομένως ο ΕΛΚΕ ΑΠΘ δεν φέρει ευθύνη για οποιαδήποτε θετική ή αποθετική ζημιά που προκλήθηκε από την χρήση του παρόντος ή των συνημμένων του λόγω ιών που έχουν περάσει σε αυτά.

Σας Ευχαριστούμε,

ΕΛΚΕ ΑΠΘ

From: Panagiotis Kartsidis <panos.kartsidis@gmail.com>
Sent: Friday, March 11, 2022 3:44 PM
To: Ethics Committee RC AUTH <ethics@rc.auth.gr>
Cc: Panagiotis Bamidis <bamidis@auth.gr>
Subject: Αίτηση διεξαγωγής μελέτης JRA 2 στα πλαίσια του έργου VITALISE

Καλησπέρα σας,

σας αποστέλλω, εκ μέρους του καθηγητή Παναγιώτη Μπαμιδί, προς έγκριση από την ΕΗΔΕ, την αίτηση και τα απαραίτητα συνοδευτικά έγγραφα της μελέτης JRA 2 που θα διεξαχθεί στα πλαίσια του ερευνητικού έργου VITALISE.

Επειδή χρειαζόμαστε αποδεικτικό κατάθεσης για ένα παραδοτέο του έργου, θα το εκτιμούσα αν απαντούσατε στο παρόν αναφέροντας ότι έχετε λάβει την αίτηση.

Ευχαριστώ,

Panagiotis-Emmanouil Kartsidis

Mathematician, PhD candidate

Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, School of Medicine

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Panagiotis Kartsidis <panos.kartsidis@gmail.com>

RE: Αίτημα προς ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ

Ethics Committee RC AUTH <ethics@rc.auth.gr>
To: "panos.kartsidis@gmail.com" <panos.kartsidis@gmail.com>
Cc: Panagiotis Bamidis <bamidis@auth.gr>

Fri, Mar 11, 2022 at 4:47 PM

Καλησπέρα σας,

με το παρόν σας ενημερώνουμε ότι έχουμε λάβει την αίτησή σας και τα απαραίτητα συνοδευτικά έγγραφα της μελέτης JRA 2, η οποία θα διεξαχθεί στα πλαίσια του ερευνητικού έργου VITALISE.

Το αίτημά σας καταχωρήθηκε με αριθμό πρωτοκόλλου 65292/11-03-2022.

Στη διάθεσή σας για οποιαδήποτε πληροφορία ή διευκρίνιση.

Από τη Γραμματεία της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ

Με εκτίμηση,

Ηράκλεια Καραγιαννίου

Γραμματεία της ΕΗΔΕ ΑΠΘ

3ης Σεπτεμβρίου, Πανεπιστημιούπολη

54636, Θεσσαλονίκη, Ελλάδα

t: (+30) 2310998427

e: ethics@rc.auth.gr

u: <http://www.rc.auth.gr>

Proof of ethics submission by LAUREA

Research permit application 1 (3)

31.1.2022

Research permit application should contain at least following elements.
If needed you may give additional information in attachments. Send the application in Word-document -format to Laurea's contact person.

Name: <i>Mika Alastalo</i>	
Title: <i>PhD, Senior Lecturer</i>	
Address: <i>Ratatie 22, 01300 Vantaa</i>	
Tel: <i>040 630 5170</i>	
E-mail: <i>mika.alastalo@laurea.fi</i>	
Date <i>21.1.2022</i>	
[Research, thesis, etc.] Author(s) /investigator(s):	PhD, Senior Lecturer Mika Alastalo MNSc, Senior Lecturer Anne Makkonen PhD, Principal Lecturer, Teemu Santonen
Degree programme / college / university:	Laurea University of Applied Sciences
Unit/ department:	
[Research, thesis, etc.] Instructor(s):	
Title of the {research, thesis, etc.}:	Transitional nursing care - simulation-based research This simulation-based research in Laurea is a part of Joint Research Activities in the Horizon 2020 Project VITALISE (Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure). VITALISE-project unites 19 partners in 11 countries and aims to harmonize Living Lab procedures and enable effective and convenient transnational and virtual access to key European health and well-being research infrastructures. Furthermore, the project aims to develop training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.
Objectives / research problem:	To explore ways of integrating observation of a patient's clinical condition, patient involvement and discharge education in transitional care. The objective of the simulation-based research is to evaluate the feasibility and the barriers that are

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▶ Domicile Vantaa

31.1.2022

	faced by a nursing student in assessing transition readiness and investigate possible suggestions and directions for support systems. Furthermore, the use of technology in facilitating transitional care and enhancing a student's learning (3D/360-cameras, wearable devices).
<p>Concise definition of what information is needed, the format in which they are needed and how the information is delivered:</p>	<p>The simulation-based research includes simulation sessions based on two patient cases and data collection before, during and after the simulation. Nursing students starting from third study semester are eligible to participate. The students will be recruited by announcing all nursing students in Laurea's campuses about the possibility to participate in simulation-based research, which will be included/integrated in their studies (will be specified in collaboration with nursing faculty). 20-40 student will be recruited, and their participation is voluntary. Simulation-based research will be organized in Tikkurila campus. Each participating student attends the activities for one working day (8 hours), and there will be approximately 10 students participating on the same day.</p> <p>Students will participate in simulation scenarios acting roles of a patient, nurses and observers. Debriefing will be organized after the simulation. There will be an expert by experience observing the simulation together with instructors/researchers and taking part in debriefing discussion.</p> <p>Data will be collection among students using a pre-simulation open questionnaire, observations during the simulations, focus-group interview and structured feedback questionnaire. Data collection is described in research plan (attachment).</p>
<p>Timetable (in two months accuracy):</p>	September 2022 - December 2022
<p>Attachments (research plan, questionnaire, framework for theme interview, privacy statement etc.):</p>	<p>Research plan (including frameworks for questionnaires, observation sheets and interviews). Information letter for the participants (in Finnish) Consent form for the participants (in Finnish) Privacy statement (in Finnish)</p>

31.1.2022

Filled by issuer of permit at Laurea	Research permit is granted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research permit is not granted	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Grounds <i>Education development; Transitional nursing care - simulation-based research.</i>			
Name of the issuer of permit: Date:	Sanna Partamies 31.1.2022			

Research permit is granted on the condition that applicant complies with legislation when processing and saving personal data. All data is confidential and provided only for purposes of survey/research in question. The applicant is responsible for securing identity and anonymity of persons in data provided. After the survey/research is completed, the applicant is responsible for deleting the data in appropriate manner.

If personal data file is created during the research (Personal Data Act -523/1999- Section 10) then applicant must comply with the provisions of law when processing and protecting of personal information. If necessary, the application must be accompanied by Scientific Research Register Description.

The applicant is responsible for providing positive decision to a person who will provide information at Laurea. Practical implementation of survey is negotiated at this point.

Proof of ethics submission by CERTH

3/31/22, 10:11 AM

Gmail - Re: Application for Ethical Approval from CERTH Research Ethics Panel

Despoina Petsani <despoinapets@gmail.com>

Re: Application for Ethical Approval from CERTH Research Ethics Panel

Sofia Segkouli <sofia@iti.gr>

31 March 2022 at 10:08

To: kopani@certh.gr, Konstantinos Votis <kvotis@iti.gr>, "atriand@iti.gr" <atriand@iti.gr>, Spiros Nikolopoulos <nikolopo@iti.gr>, Stefanos Vrochidis <stefanos@iti.gr>, "ioulialtalaz@iti.gr" <ioulialtalaz@iti.gr>, Katerina Vaxevani <kvaxevani@iti.gr>, Despoina Petsani <despoinapets@gmail.com>

Dear Ms Kopani,

We are kindly asking you to send the attached protocol to ethics committee members requesting their approval for pilot operations' performance in terms of VITALIZE project, more specifically in respect to WP6 activities concerning 'Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care'.

Thank you very much in advance,

Best regards,

Segkouli Sofia

Dr. Sofia Segkouli
Building A - Office 1.9
Information Technologies Institute
Centre of Research & Technology - Hellas
6th km Harilaou - Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece
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Proof of ethics submission by McGill

Formulaire - Nouveau projet avec recrutement de participants - CRIR

Titre du protocole : **Holistic evaluation of the determinants of mobility to enhance social and work participation: Platform trial of the Electronic Mobility Monitoring and Intervention (EMMI) Portal**

Numéro(s) de projet : **MP-50-2022-1411**

Formulaire : **F11a-CRIR-2104**

Identifiant Nagano : **EMMI_Holistic evaluation of the determinants of mobility to enhance social and work participation: Platform trial of the Electronic Mobility Monitoring and Intervention Portal**

Date de dépôt initial du formulaire : **2022-03-18**

Date de dépôt final du formulaire : **2022-03-18**

Chercheur principal (au CER Éval) : **Madame Sara Ahmed, Ph.D.**

Statut du formulaire : **Formulaire déposé**

Date d'approbation du projet par le CER : **projet non approuvé**

Renseignements généraux

1. **Indiquez le titre du projet de recherche selon le protocole.**

Holistic evaluation of the determinants of mobility to enhance social and work participation: Platform trial of the Electronic Mobility Monitoring and Intervention (EMMI) Portal

2. **Indiquez le nom du chercheur principal.**

Dans le cas d'un projet étudiant (collégial, premier cycle, maîtrise, doctorat, post-doctorat ou travail d'érudition de type recherche), le responsable du projet est le professeur encadrant la recherche de l'étudiant.

Ahmed, Sara

3. **Le chercheur principal est-il affilié à l'un des instituts universitaires (IU), centre affilié universitaire (CAU) ou centre de recherche (CR) du CCSMTL, au CRIR ou membre du CMDP du CCSMTL ?**

Oui

Veillez préciser quelle(s) affiliation(s) :

- Institut universitaire sur les dépendances (IUD)
- Centre de recherche de l'Institut universitaire de gériatrie de Montréal (CRIUGM)
- Institut universitaire Jeunes en difficulté (IUJD)
- Institut universitaire sur la réadaptation en déficience physique de Montréal (IURDPM) du CRIR
- Autres établissements du Centre de recherche interdisciplinaire en réadaptation du Montréal métropolitain (CRIR)
- Centre de recherche de Montréal sur les inégalités sociales et les discriminations (CREMIS)
- Centre de recherche en santé publique (CRéSP)
- Conseil des médecins, dentistes et pharmaciens (CMDP) du CCSMTL
- Direction régionale santé publique (DRSP) du CCSMTL

Veillez préciser à quel autre établissement du CRIR le chercheur principal est affilié :

- CIUSSS du Centre-Ouest-de-l'Île-de-Montréal, Centre de réadaptation Lethbridge-Layton-Mackay
- CISSS de Laval, Hôpital juif de réadaptation
- CISSS de la Montérégie-Centre, Institut Nazareth et Louis-Braille

Proof of ethics submission by UPM

Gmail - documentacion comité ético - proyecto VITALISE

<https://mail.google.com/mail/u/1/?ik=df1aacc3a&view=pt&search=a...>

Gloria Cea Sánchez <gloriaceas@gmail.com>

documentacion comité ético - proyecto VITALISE

Gloria Cea Sánchez <gcea@lst.tfo.upm.es>

7 de febrero de 2022, 6:22

Para: Secretaria Adjunto VRa Investigación UPM <secretaria.adjunto.vinvestigacion@upm.es>

Cc: Ivana Lombroni <ilombroni@lst.tfo.upm.es>, Beatriz Merino <bmerino@lst.tfo.upm.es>

Buenos días Julia,

Siguiendo las indicaciones de la web del comité, os hacemos llegar tres ficheros pdf que con los formularios de solicitud de valoración: **Modelo 6** + documentos específicos que en este caso son el de **Protección de Datos Personales** y el de **Investigación biomédica con humanos o con muestras de origen humano**. No los unimos en 1 solo documento por el panel de firmas, pero decidnos si fuera necesario.

Por favor confirma la correcta recepción del email y agradecemos si nos pudieras dar un tiempo estimado en el que recibirimos la respuesta, nos lo solicitan desde el proyecto.

Saludos

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[El texto citado está oculto]

www.lst.tfo.upm.es

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3 adjuntos

- **VITALISE Formulario_investigacion_biomedica_2021 _ Muestras origen humano.pdf**
453K
- **VITALISE MODELO6.2_3- COMPLETO.pdf**
205K
- **VITALISE PROTECCION-DATOS-2017_2.pdf**
398K